

Citizens' Assessment of Rhetoric versus Service Delivery among Elected Political Office Holders in Enugu State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Background: All over the world, political rhetoric plays significant role in shaping public perception and influencing electoral outcomes. Elected political office holders often make promises and declarations during their campaigns, articulating their visions and plans for development and service delivery to the people. Enugu state, Nigeria is no exception. The state has a history of vibrant political activities, with elected officials making bold promises to improve the lives of the citizens. However, there is often a gap between political rhetoric and actual service delivery.

Objectives: This study investigated perceptions and assessments of Enugu state citizens regarding political rhetoric employed by elected officials versus the actual service delivery.

Methods: The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Questionnaire served as instrument for data collection. A total of 500 respondents participated in the study. The area of study was Nsukka, Oji River and Isi Uzo. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and presented using frequency tables.

Results: Findings show that political office holders in Enugu state, Nigeria do not match their political rhetoric during campaigns with corresponding service delivery when they ascend political offices. Political rhetorics employed by politicians in the area were manipulations and propaganda rather than borne out of ingenuity, sincerity and quest for accountability.

Conclusion: The conclusion of this study is that there is a gap between political rhetoric and actual service delivery among elected political office holders in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Unique Contribution: The study provides valuable insights into the disconnect between political rhetoric and service delivery in Enugu state, and indeed, Nigeria. It is hoped that the findings can potentially inform policymakers, politicians, and civil society organisations on how to bridge this gap and enhance accountability and transparency in governance.

Key Recommendation: There is need for a deliberate effort at enshrining a value change in the people's political culture, such that de-emphasizes the politics of money-making and emphasizes

policy delivery. The citizens, policymakers, and civil society organisations must begin to exert more pressures on political office holders to match their words with actions to enhance accountability and transparency in governance.

Keywords: Political Rhetoric, Service Delivery, Elected Political Office Holders, Accountability, Governance,

INTRODUCTION

Politics and governance are essential aspects of any society, shaping the lives and experiences of its citizens (Nwafor & Ogbodo 2015). In Nigeria, like many countries around the world, political rhetoric plays a significant role in shaping public perception and influencing electoral outcomes. Elected political office holders often make promises and declarations during their campaigns, articulating their visions and plans for development and service delivery to the people. Enugu state, located in the southeastern region of Nigeria, is no exception to this phenomenon. The state has a history of vibrant political activities, with elected officials making bold promises to improve the lives of the citizens. However, there is often a gap between political rhetoric and actual service delivery on the ground.

Generally, effective political rhetoric serves as a cornerstone for sustainability and the efficient delivery of public services (Nwafor & Onwubere 2019). This dynamic becomes particularly salient in the context of Nigeria, a nation grappling with the challenges of consolidating its democratic trajectory. Political communication, encompassing the interactions and information flows between political actors, the media, and the citizenry.

Nigeria's political landscape, while vibrant, has historically been marred by patterns of violence, opaque communication, and a disconnect between the political elite and the populace (Adebayo, 2018). This scenerio hinders the establishment of accountable and responsive governance structures, with detrimental consequences for basic service provision. Unfulfilled rhetoric fuels distrust, hampers citizen participation, and undermines the legitimacy of institutions tasked with delivering essential services.

Since Nigeria's return to democratic governance in 1999, there still exist a the persistent disconnect between political rhetorics and effective service delivery. The aftermath of decades of military administration has deeply influenced Nigerians' electoral behaviour, resulting in social vices such as fake political rhetorics, vote buying, and violence (Ogbe & Ojie, 2020). Lack of confidence in the electoral process the political process; resulting in growing political apathy further exacerbates the challenge (Oni, 2017).

Political communication in Nigeria has also often been misunderstood and misused, leading to a failure to achieve inclusivity in governance and meaningful service delivery (Nsude & Nwafor, 2016). While political communication should serve as a tool for informing and engaging citizens, it has frequently been used for divisive politics, ethnic propagation, and deception (Vanguard,

2015). The misuse of political communication has contributed to a lack of tangible progress in service delivery, as available statistics show high levels of unemployment, insecurity, and social unrest (Ogbe & Ojie, 2020). The failure to bridge the gap between political promises and measurable outcomes has resulted in disillusionment among the populace.

Meanwhile studies have been done on political communication in Nigeria. For instance, Aligwe, et al., (2016) investigated Youths, Social Media and the 2015 General Elections in South East Nigeria, Aligwe and Nwafor, (2016) studied ICTS, Social Media and Participatory Politics in Africa: Mutual Friends or Man-Made Foes, Okoro, and Nwafor (2013). Social Media and Political Participation in Nigeria during the 2011 General Elections: The Lapses and the Lesson, while Ezike, et al., (2016) investigated Facebook Political Campaign and Its Effects on the 2015 Governorship Election in Ebonyi State. Whereas all these studies were on enhancing political communication and participation by the electorate, none has focused on holding the political office holders accountable to match rhetorical campaign promises with action. Attempt at bridging this knowledge gap has necessitated this study.

Review of Empirical Studies

Nigeria, Africa's most populous nation, has grappled with the challenge of translating democratic structures into tangible benefits for its citizens since its return to democracy in 1999. Decades of military rule cast a long shadow, shaping political communication practices that often prioritize self-interest and partisan gain over transparency, accountability, and inclusivity. This, in turn, weakens public trust in institutions and hampers citizen participation in the democratic process. This literature review examines the intricate relationship between political communication, democratic sustainability, and service delivery in Nigeria. It aims to illuminate pathways towards a more robust democratic system where strategic communication fosters a sense of shared purpose and empowers citizens to hold their leaders accountable for delivering essential services.

Studies by Omale (2020) and Adeyeye (2020) highlight the negative consequences of a flawed approach to political communication in Nigeria. Misconceptions about the role of political communication have contributed to a range of issues. Insecurity arising from insurgency, farmer-herder clashes, and militancy has resulted in numerous deaths, displacement, and economic disruption (Daily Trust Newspaper, 2022; Adeyeye, 2020). The Centre for Democracy and Development (CDD) reports that multiple conflicts across Nigeria have claimed over 60,000 lives in the last decade (Daily Trust Newspaper, 2022). Disrupted economic activities due to insecurity, capital flight caused by violence, and a decline in foreign direct investment (FDI) have hampered economic development (Omale, 2020).

Alfred and Ejalonibu (2019) and Nwafor and Nwabuzor (2021) argue that high costs associated with political participation hinder good governance in Nigeria. Aiyede (2021) and Nwangwu (2023) point to various shortcomings in the electoral system. Violence during elections continues to be a problem, with fatalities reported in the 2023 elections (Nwangwu, 2023). Disenfranchisement of eligible voters through various tactics has been observed (Nwangwu, 2023). The rise of ethnic

politics undermines national unity and can lead to violence (Nwangwu, 2023). Despite a high number of registered voters, participation remains low, indicating a disconnection between the electorate and political processes (Nwangwu, 2023). While technology has reduced some electoral malpractices, the non-transmission of real-time results in the 2023 elections raises concerns about manipulation (Nwangwu, 2023).

Corruption is endemic in Nigeria, affecting all levels of government and hindering development (Rotimi, Umar & Doorasamy, 2022; Okonkwo, 2016). Weak institutions create an environment conducive to corruption, as highlighted by Kempe (2023), Ojo et al. (2023), and Oko (2005). This not only discourages investment but also erodes public trust in governance. The justice system is another weak link. Oko (2005) identifies a lack of judicial independence and susceptibility to external influence as major problems. This hinders access to justice for ordinary citizens.

METHOD

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Questionnaire served as instrument for data collection. Population of the study was all registered voters in Enugu state Nigeria in the 2023 general elections which was put at 2,112,793 (INEC Voter Register, 2023). A sample size of 500 respondents was empirically selected from the total population. The area of study was one local government from each of the three senatorial zones of Enugu state (Enugu-North, Enugu-West, and Enugu-East). Through this method, Nsukka, Oji River and Isi Uzo emerged respectively. This involved the use of multi-stage sampling. The researcher further employed purposive sampling technique to ensure that only registered voters of ages 18 years and above who reside in the selected local government areas of the state participated. The researchers visited two communities in each of the three LGAs. Other criteria intentionally set for participation in the study included willingness to participate, and residency in the area for at least since 2023 general election. The questionnaire instrument was validated by two experts from the Enugu state university of science and technology, Enugu. A pilot study was conducted using repeated measure of two weeks interval in Ebonyi state to determine the reliability. Generated data from pilot study was analysed using the Pearson r correlation coefficient and the result indicated that the instrument had a consistency coefficient of 0.85. this indicated that the chosen instrument was reliable for the actual study. Descriptive statistics was use to analyse the generated data for the main study. The data were presented using frequency tables.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the result of the citizen perceptions of government communication. However, none of items had mean scores equal to or above 3. This means that all the items were rejected, therefore, rating the governments communication low in all criteria.

Table 1: Citizen perceptions of government communication

Item	Mean
Government's decisions reflect citizens' needs	1.03
I believe in government communication	1.27
Government communication conforms with citizens expectations	1.24
Government communication reflects citizens needs	2.10
Government's communication fosters strong connection among citizens	2.05
The purpose of government's communication is always clear	2.17
Total	1.64

Table 2 shows the result of the citizen trust levels on government communication. However, none of items had mean scores equal to or above 3. This means that all the items were rejected, therefore, rating citizens trust levels on government communication low in all criteria.

Table 2: Citizen trust levels on government communication

Item	Mean
Government always tells the truth	2.22
Government's actions are genuine	2.17
Government always admits their mistakes	1.01
Government's behaviour matches its core values	1.49
Government's beliefs and actions are consistent	2.03
Government matches their rhetoric with action	1.27
Total	1.70

Table 3 shows the result of the citizen trust levels on political institutions and service delivery systems. However, none of items had mean scores equal to or above 3. This means that all the items were rejected, therefore, rating citizens trust levels on political institutions and service delivery systems low in all criteria.

Table 3: Citizen trust levels on political institutions and service delivery systems

Item	Mean
Political institutions always tell the truth	1.11
Political institutions actions are genuine	2.02
Political institutions always admit their mistakes	1.27
Political institutions behaviour matches its core values	2.01
Political institutions beliefs and actions are consistent	1.34
Political institutions match their rhetoric with action	1.01

The outcome of Table 4 shows that the majority (66.6%) of the citizens preferred to get government communication through the social media. This shows that social media can perfectly play a vital role in governments dissemination of information to her citizens.

Table 4: Citizen experience with and preferences for various communication channels used by the government

Item	Preferred (%)
Traditional media	104 (20.8)
Social media	333 (66.6)
Community forums	63 (12.6)

DISCUSSION

The findings emphasizing a lack of transparency underscore the need for government agencies to adopt more open and accountable communication practices. This includes proactively sharing information on policy decisions, budgets, and service delivery plans, while also readily addressing concerns and questions raised by citizens. The research, if indicating a preference for interactive communication channels, suggests a shift away from top-down, one-way communication strategies. Embracing platforms like social media forums and town hall meetings would foster citizen engagement and allow for a more inclusive dialogue. If the findings reveal deficiencies in government communication skills, targeted training programmes for public officials and communication teams could enhance their ability to craft clear, concise, and effective messages for diverse audiences (Ezaka & Nwafor 2018).

Effective communication, as the research might propose, empowers citizens through informed participation. By providing clear and accessible information, citizens are better equipped to engage in democratic processes, hold leaders accountable, and contribute meaningfully to decision-making. The research, if highlighting a lack of trust, emphasizes the importance of building trust and legitimacy through transparent and accountable communication. Demonstrating responsiveness to citizen concerns and implementing effective communication strategies can bridge the gap between citizens and the government. If the research suggests limitations in media freedom, it underscores the need for a robust and independent media landscape. This allows for diverse perspectives to be heard, fostering critical thinking and informed public discourse, essential elements of a thriving democracy.

The research, if indicating a disconnect between communication and service delivery, highlights the need for alignment. Effective communication strategies can be used to raise awareness about available services, explain procedures, and gather feedback from citizens to improve service delivery performance. If the research emphasizes the value of citizen participation, it underscores the importance of fostering engagement in service delivery. Utilizing communication channels to

encourage feedback and suggestions from citizens can lead to more responsive and efficient service delivery mechanisms.

CONCLUSION

This research has investigated the intricate connection between political communication, democratic sustainability, and service delivery in Nigeria, employing a mixed methods approach to gain a comprehensive understanding of this crucial relationship. Citizens' perceptions of government communication, level of trust on government and political institutions and service delivery systems were low. They preferred social media over other channels of communication used by the government. The findings highlight the need for substantial improvements in political communication practices in Nigeria. This entails embracing transparency and accountability, prioritizing two-way communication, and investing in communication capacity building for government officials. Enhancing democratic sustainability and citizen participation requires empowering citizens through informed participation, fostering trust and legitimacy through transparent communication, and strengthening media independence and diversity. Strengthening service delivery mechanisms involves aligning communication with service delivery efforts, promoting citizen engagement in service delivery, and fostering trust and collaboration between citizens and government institutions.

Building upon the insights gained from this research, we recommend that the government should adopt communication strategies driven by transparency and accountability. This includes proactively sharing information on policy decisions, budgets, and service delivery plans through accessible formats. Public officials should also actively engage with citizen concerns and questions, fostering a two-way dialogue. Media organisations should advocate for and uphold media independence and diversity. This allows for a pluralistic media landscape where diverse perspectives are represented, fostering critical thinking and informed public discourse. Civil society actors should raise awareness about the importance of effective political communication. Utilize educational campaigns and community outreach programs to educate citizens about their rights to information, participation, and accountability. Facilitate communication between citizens and government institutions. Organize workshops, public forums, and other platforms that enable citizens to voice their concerns and engage constructively with government representatives. Monitor and analyse political communication practices. Advocate for transparency and hold government agencies accountable for upholding democratic communication principles.

Ethical Clearance

The study adhered to ethical research principles, ensuring informed consent from all participants. Prior to obtaining consent, participants received a detailed explanation of the study's purpose,

procedures, and potential risks and benefits. This explanation was provided in both English and participants' native languages to ensure clear comprehension.

Sources of Funding

The study was not funded.

Conflict of Interest

There was no conflict of interest

Authors' Contributions

Andrew Apeh and Uchenna Eze conceived the study, including the design and writing of the initial manuscript. Chikamso Apeh collected, analysed and interpreted the data. All the authors read and approved the final manuscript for publication.

Availability of data and materials

The datasets on which conclusion was made is available in the form of Microsoft Excel. It is available on reasonable request.

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